

Cosolvency Studies of Polyethylene. Part—I : Lowering of Cloud Temperature in Cosolvent Mixtures

NITA VIDYARTHI* (nee DAS) and SANTI. R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

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Polyethylene, though quite insoluble in any single solvent at near room temperature, was earlier found to dissolve in a mixture of two non-solvents. A few such cosolvent pairs, including some new ones, have been studied in details with respect to cloud temperature and the existence of optimum solvent composition as judged by a maximum in intrinsic viscosity. The failure of Gee's criterion for cosolvency has been pointed out. The results have also been discussed, with only partial success, with respect to an equation derived by Deb and Palit, based on the thermodynamic approach of Scott. Probably, some kind of specific interaction and structure formation play an important role in such cosolvency.

A number of cosolvents for the difficultly soluble polyethylene (PE) were reported in our previous communication¹. This communication reports an extension of the above study to more samples (some fractionated) in five new cosolvent pairs with respect to variation of cloud temperature and $[\eta]$ with solvent composition.

Experimental

Materials : The polyethylene samples D-H are from Union Carbide, USA and WSG-22, WNF-15 and RQ-161 were supplied by I.C.I. (India) to whom our thanks are due. All solvents, excepting CS₂, THF and C₆H₆ were of analytical grade and were not subjected to further purification but distilled under anhydrous condition before use. CS₂, THF and C₆H₆ were purified by standard^{1,2} methods.

Fractionation of the polymer and measurement of cloud temperature in the cosolvent mixtures were carried out according to the methods stated earlier¹.

Determination of molecular weight : Molecular weights of the various polyethylene fractions were determined by measuring the osmotic pressures of their xylene solutions at 60° in a Hewlett-Packard 501 high speed membrane osmometer using 0.08 membrane with the help of the following equation

$$\left(\frac{\pi}{C}\right)_{c \rightarrow 0} = \frac{RT}{M_n} \quad \dots (1)$$

(the symbols have the usual significance)

Estimation of methyl groups (per 1000 methylene) of the fractionated polymer : The estimation of -CH₃ groups in the polymer samples was done by ir spectroscopy from the ratio of absorptions due to methyl and methylene groups with the help

of suitable samples, with known percentage of methyl groups, used as standards. For all the compounds studied, fractionated or unfractionated (experimental and standard), a sharp peak was observed at 1370 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 1390 cm⁻¹. The spectra of the standard samples (D, E, F, G) showed that there is a correlation between the number of the methyl groups per 1000 CH₂ and the ratio of the absorptions at 1370 and 1390 cm⁻¹. Plotting of A 1370/A 1390 against the number of methyl groups gives a straight line and this plot was used for estimating the number of methyl groups per 1000 CH₂ in the experimental samples. The spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer with NaCl optics.

Measurement of intrinsic viscosity : Intrinsic viscosities were calculated using the equation

$$\eta_{sp}/c = [\eta] + k'[\eta]^2 c \quad \dots (2)$$

where the solution viscosities were determined by measuring the flow times in Ubbelohde dilution viscometer for which the kinetic energy corrections are negligible.

Results and Discussion

Minimum cloud temperature (T_c)_{min} : In our previous preliminary work¹ xylene-CS₂ (1) was reported to be the most efficient cosolvent pair followed by cyclohexane-CS₂ (2). The work has been extended to five other cosolvent pairs, viz., toluene-CS₂ (3), benzene-CS₂ (4), chloroform-CS₂ (5), carbontetrachloride-CS₂ (6) and tetrahydrofuran(THF)-CS₂ (7). We were compelled to use CS₂ as the second component as we are yet to find another solvent with such powerful codissolving action on PE. Thiophene was found to be a very poor substitute for CS₂. Further, CS₂ with

*Present address : Department of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College, 30 Park Street, Calcutta-16.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYETHYLENE SAMPLES STUDIED

Polymer Designation	**Polymer crystallinity %	Melt index	Density gm/ml	$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-3}$	$\text{CH}_2/1000 \text{CH}_3^*$
WSG-22	50	70.0	0.918	21.0	40 ^a
WNF-15	54	7.0	0.919	28.0	—
RQ-161	51	data not available	data not available	24-28	—
D	64	3.5	0.918	81.0	30 [*]
E	67	3.5	0.922	33.00	25 [*]
F	61	23	0.914	25	35 [*]
G	58	300	0.910	12	40 [*]
H	42	>10 ⁴	0.885	4	60 [*]
FRACTIONS					
1	data not available	data not available	0.918	186.0	25 ^a
2	"	"	"	47.40	28 ^a
3	"	"	"	46.40	36 ^a
4	"	"	"	25.10	37 ^a
5	"	"	"	20.38	38 ^a
6	"	"	"	19.14	39 ^a

* Estimated from density.

** % Crystallinity for all samples being supplied by manufacturers ;

^a Estimated from ir studies (vide experimental).

TABLE 2— $(T_c)_{\min}$ OF CS_2 -CO-SOLVENT SYSTEMS

Samples	THF °C	CHCl_3 °C	CCl_4 °C	Xylene °C	Cyclohexane °C	Benzene °C	Toluene °C	$(T_c)_{\min}$ Cyclohexane TCE °C
WSG-22	17.0(50)*	19.0(45)	26.0(40)	26.5(25)	28.0(45)	34.5(30)	38.5(40)	35.5(30)**
D	15.5(45)	18.0(45)	25.0(40)	27.0(25)	28.5(50)	34.5(30)	25.0(15)	45.0(30)
E		17.5(40)	24.0(45)	28.0(25)	29.5(50)	37.0(30)	39.5(25)	48.5(35)
F		17.5(45)	24.5(40)	24.0(25)	27.5(50)		39.0(25)	38.0(35)
WNF-15				39.0(45)			—	—
RQ-161				38.5(20)			—	—
G							25 (15)	
H	22.0(50)						39.5(25)	
FRACTIONS								
1		23.0(45)	—	—	—			
2	23.5(45)	32.0(50)	22.0(40)	25.5(20)	25.5(50)			
3	22.5(55)	28.0(45)	26.0(40)	28.5(25)	25.0(50)			
4	18.5(50)	17.0(40)	25.0(40)	26.0(20)	24.0(55)			
5	21.5(45)	24.0(45)	28.0(45)	27.5(20)	18.0(45)			
6	22.0(55)	18.5(45)	23.0(45)	27.0(20)	23.0(50)			

* figures in parentheses indicate % CS_2 by volume.

** figures in parentheses indicate % TCE.

pyridine, dioxane and chlorobenzene had no effect on lowering T_c , and in chlorobenzene precipitation results.

A few more unfractionated polyethylene samples, whose characteristics are shown in Table 1, were also included. WSG-22 of medium high molecular weight was selected for fractionation and the fractions were studied individually in cosolvent pairs No. (1), (2), (5), (6) and (7).

The highest fraction was found insoluble in all these cosolvent pairs near room temperature excepting CHCl_3 - CS_2 , but its supply being meagre, it could not be used for T_c studies.

The T_c values are summarized in Table 2 and a few typical T_c versus composition curves are

represented in Figs. 1-4. The trend of the curves is more or less the same, there being a deepwell concave to the composition axis, whose minimum point is the optimum solvent composition (OSC) and the corresponding temperature is $(T_c)_{\min}$. It may be noted that the minimum cloud temperature is often (vide Table 2) as low as in the twenties and in some cases even below it, for example in THF- CS_2 and CHCl_3 - CS_2 with unfractionated PE.

It was found somewhat unexpectedly that some lower fractions sometimes are less soluble than the higher fractions (Table 2); for example, fraction 5 in CCl_4 - CS_2 system has a $(T_c)_{\min}$ of 28° whereas for fraction 2, the $(T_c)_{\min}$ is 22°. Also, the unfractionated sample, WSG-22, has a $(T_c)_{\min}$ as low as 17° in THF- CS_2 , whereas the fractions derived

Fig. 1. Plot of cloud temperature T_c of fractionated samples vs CS_2 content in $CHCl_3$.

Fig. 2. Plot of cloud temperature T_c of fractionated samples vs CS_2 content in cyclohexane.

Fig. 3. Plot of cloud temperature T_c of unfractionated samples vs CS_2 content in CCl_4 .

Fig. 4. Plot of cloud temperature T_c of unfractionated samples vs CS_2 content in THF.

from it do not exhibit such low $(T_c)_{min}$ values. This evidently means that (i) fractions are not identical in structure, and (ii) lower fractions have codissolving power for higher fractions—a fact well known in the varnish industry.

Variation of the optimum solvent composition:
It is a remarkable fact that percent CS_2 in the

Fig. 5. Plot of cloud temperature T_c of unfractionated samples vs CS_2 content in toluene.

optimum solvent composition in a given cosolvent pair is more or less the same (within $\pm 5\%$) for all samples of PE. Out of 60 systems studied, only two exceptions were found in the case of WNF-15 in xylene- CS_2 ¹ and WSG-22 in toluene- CS_2 (Fig. 5; Table 2). In both these cases, the fall in T_c is small and the minimum is not well defined.

With respect to change of molecular weight, the OSC does not show any systematic change. This is probably expected because the polarity of the molecule remains essentially unaffected by a change in the degree of polymerization. The solubility of both the fractionated and the unfractionated polymer could not be correlated with the number of methyl groups in the sample, though it has been shown⁸ that the solubility of polymers is highly sensitive to even small degrees of branching, in the sense that an isolated branched macromolecule is characterized by a higher degree of local concentration of segments than an isolated linear molecule of the same type and the same molecular weight in the same solvent.

Corroboration of OSC derived from $[\eta]_{max}$ values as well as $(T_c)_{min}$ values: Palit *et al*⁵ and quite a few other workers^{1,4,6-10} have shown that $(T_c)_{min}$ corresponds to a maximum in $[\eta]$ which is therefore the index of solvent power. This concept of agreement between $[\eta]_{max}$ and OSC, tested earlier¹, has been examined in other cosolvents¹¹.

Theoretical :

(i) *Solubility parameter and cosolvency:* It is evident that in our case δ plays hardly any role and the cosolvency is due to a specific interaction with

CS_2 . This is evident from the fact that CS_2 ($\delta=10$) in combination with many solvents with a wide range of δ values, which may be higher or lower than the δ value of polyethylene ($\delta=9$), exhibit co-dissolving power on PE. Hence, agreement with Gee's condition¹²

$$\delta_{(nonsolvent)1} < \delta_{polymer} < \delta_{(nonsolvent)2}$$

in a few cases may be regarded as merely fortuitous.

Even introducing the concept of energy density matching by using the relation

$$\delta_{mixture} = \phi_1 \delta_1 + \phi_2 \delta_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

(where ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are volume fractions) does not improve the matter to any remarkable extent because if δ_1 and δ_2 are both greater than $\delta_{polymer}$, merely giving weightage to them does not help the situation in any way.

(ii) *In the light of a more refined concept:* In order to examine how far Scott's formulation for a ternary system can be utilised to obtain an expression for the best solvent composition, Deb and Palit¹³ proposed the following

$$(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 v_1 - (\delta_2 - \delta_3)^2 v_2 - (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \{ (v_1 - v_2) \phi_1^2 - 2v_1 \phi_1 + v_1 \} = 0 \quad \dots (4)$$

where δ_i s represent the cohesive energy density of the i -th components, v_1 and v_2 represent the molar volumes of the two liquids and the ϕ s are the respective volume fractions.

The observed optimum solvent compositions for the different cosolvent systems have been compared with those obtained theoretically from the equation of Deb and Palit¹³.

The agreement is only good to fair in many cases but hopelessly poor in benzene- CS_2 , $CHCl_3$ - CS_2 and THF- CS_2 where the theoretical prediction of ϕ_1 (volume fraction of solvent at the optimum) becomes unrealistic, i.e., greater than unity. However, it may be pointed out that this equation is quite unsuitable for such a test as it is highly sensitive to δ_3 . We may therefore calculate δ_3 from our experimental data and compare it with the known value of $\delta_{polymer}$ —a procedure also followed by Hilderbrand¹⁴ in some cases during development of the δ concept owing to the same difficulty. The agreement at least for CS_2 systems may be considered good, the values ranging from 9 to 9.6 against the literature value of 9.0 (which is also an estimate). Thus, cosolvency studies may provide a method of determination of CED or δ of polymers. It appears that in such ternary systems, some kind of structure formation and microheterogeneity may be responsible for the unusual observations and the difficulty in theoretical interpretation.

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